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Job Productivity Skills Required By Business Educators For Effective Recruitment And Selection Process In Tertiary Institutions In Delta State

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the job productivity skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The job productivity skills examined were time management skills and digital skills. Similarly, the moderating influence of gender, and type of institution were investigated. Two research questions were raised and answered, and two hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted the descriptive survey research approach. The population of the study was 132 business educators in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The sample size was 132 and the census sampling technique was adopted. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire and was validated by three experts. The Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient (PPMC) was used to ascertain the reliability of the instrument and reliability coefficient of 0.84 was obtained. Data collected were analyzed using Mean, Standard Deviation and t-test Statistics. The findings indicated that business educators require job productivity skills such as time management and digital skill for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Also, the study revealed that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of business educators on time management skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State based on gender among others. It was concluded that business educators requires job productivity skills such as time management skills, digital skills for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Hence, it was recommended among others that curriculum planners should ensure the inclusion of courses that will promote job productivity skills in the curriculum of business education. With this, the business educators will be able to possess these job productivity skills required by employers for recruiting and selecting candidates for employment in organizations.

Keywords: Job Productivity Skills, Business Educators, Recruitment, Selection Process

INTRODUCTION

Job productivity is a measure of the quantity and quality of work done, considering the cost of resources used. Also, job productivity refers to the efficiency and effectiveness of an individual or organization in completing tasks, achieving goals, and producing desired outputs within a given timeframe. It is a measure of how well resources such as time effect, and materials are utilized to generate desired outcomes. Tangen (2015), attested that job productivity can be used to refer to any idea that takes into account a company's and its operations' success. Job productivity can relate to the

actual outputs or results of specific activities, the manner in which an activity is executed, or the ability to produce outcomes

Business educators are those lecturers that teach business education courses in higher institutions (Akpojotor, 2023). However, Utoware and Igberaharha (2023), described business education as a vocational and skill based educational programme which is promoted widely for its relevance in the current competitive global market and equips learners with requisite competencies for employers of labor, entrepreneurship and exposed students to functional and suitable skills, knowledge, attitudes and values that enables the students to operate in the environment they find themselves for self-reliance and in turn national development. These business educators that teach business education courses are expected to possess certain amount of job productivity skills at the point of recruitment and selection process. These job productivity skills include, time management skills, communication skills, problem solving skills, teamwork skills and digital skills among others. With regards to this study, the job productivity skills considered are time management skills and digital skills.

Business educators need effectual time management skills to enable them carry out multiple tasks, prioritize responsibilities, and maximum productivity to be carried out. Effective time management skills are crucial for achieving goals, reducing stress and increasing productivity. The following are some of the time management skills required by the business educators: prioritization, scheduling, organization, avoidance of procrastination, focus and concentration, delegation, adaptability among others. Lukevich and Wigmore, (2024) upheld in his work that organization that have employees that possess effective time management skills stand to have happier employees, improved creativity, less absenteeism, lower turnover rate, increased productivity and enhanced reputation. While Okoro (2018) found in his study that time management strategies needed by university Business Education graduates for successful business are planning the job to be done and assigning responsibilities to subordinates. Also, Grimm (2011) found that a well time management skill staff increases organizational productivity.

Apparently, business educators are oblige to possess digital skills to enable them function properly in this 21st century. Digital skills are referred to as abilities to effectively use digital technologies such as computers, smartphone's, and the internet to access, evaluate and create information. Business educators are expected to possess the following digital skills: basic computer skills, internet skills, email skills, word processing skills, spreadsheets skills presentation skills, digital communication skills and data analysis skills. As in today's digital age, developing digital skills is important for personal and professional success. Ezoem et al. (2024) found in their study that digital marketing competencies and digital social media competencies are highly needed of business education graduates employability prospect and job creation in Delta State. Also, that gender and years of teaching experience do not significantly influenced lecturers of business education mean ratings regarding digital marketing and digital social media competencies needed of business education graduates for employability prospect and job creation in Delta State.

Furthermore, Dibbari and Lawrence (2023) conducted a study on business educators' perception of digital skills required by office technology and management students for employability and found that digital skills were required for employability by OTM students based on the opinion of business educators. Also found was that electronic records management skills are required by OTM students for employability in North-East Nigeria. In another study conducted by Ukata and Amini (2022) on digital entrepreneurial skills acquired by business education undergraduates for decent works in tertiary institutions in Rivers State they discovered that the digital marketing and social media skills acquired was very low level. Also, that business education undergraduates differ in their mean rating due to personal factors.

Hence, employers of labor in this modern times require certain job productivity skills from their employees (Business educators) as requirement for effective recruitment and selection process. According to Gamage (2015), recruitment and selection process helps create a pool of job applicants and sort adequate people to work for positive organizational outcomes. In a study conducted by Ekwoaba, Ugochkwu and Ndubuisi, (2015) they discovered in their work that recruitment and selection criteria have significant effect on organization's performance.

The moderating variables of gender and type of institutions was use to moderate the job productivity skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Gender refers to socially constructed roles, behaviours and expectations

associated with being male or female. It is the features of boys, girls, men, and women that are socially constructed. Igbongidi (2021) examined skills required for recruitment and selection process of higher education sector and its impact on organizational outcomes and found that equal opportunity was given to male and female employees' base on merit. Also found was that recruitment and selection practices led to employment of competent staff.

Type of institution refers to educational institutions such as universities and colleges of education. Akpojotor (2023) carried out a study on job design techniques and job satisfaction of universities and colleges of education business educators in Edo and Delta states and discovered from the study that there was no significant difference in the relationship between job design techniques and job satisfaction of universities and colleges of education business educators in Edo and Delta states. Okon (2023) in his study on digital skills needed by business education students for effective job performance found that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of respondents on digital skills needed by business education students for effective performance of job in the colleges of education and universities in Enugu State.

Statement of the Problem

In today's highly competitive and versatile labour market, job seekers are expected to possess a high amount of set skills apart from their academic qualifications that will make them to be outstanding in the labour market. Apparently, organization success would be highly dependent on the personnel that handle employment process by recruiting the right candidates with strong job productivity skills. Hence, business educators are anticipated to possess job productivity skills that will make them to be recruited and selected for employment in organizations including tertiary institutions.

These job productivity skills include, time management skills, task management skills, problem solving skills, teamwork skills, communication skills and digital skills. In quite a lot of visit to certain institutions, the researcher observed that business educators are complaining that most of the applicants employed in the department do not possess the necessary skills required for job productivity. What could be the cause of this deficiency? Could it be that they did not possess these job productivity skills before their recruitment and selection for employment? Or could it be that those in charge of recruitment and selection process failed to do the needful? The need to provide answers to these questions led to the study which is job productivity skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study is to determine the job productivity skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Specifically, the study sought to ascertain:

1. Time management skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State.
2. Digital skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Research question

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What are the time management skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State?
2. What are the digital skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and guided the study at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of business educators on time management skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State based on gender.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of business educators on digital skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State based on type of institution.

Theoretical Framework

Human capital theory was adopted for the study. The theory was propounded by Theodore W. Schultz in 1961, he stated that organization can only grows when the personnel department focus on recruiting applicant that have necessary skills that are required for the job. He also emphasize that individual should possess skills outside certificate acquired from institutions as employees are workforce of every organization, therefore, it is necessary to do the needful in order to avoid expensive errors.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND PROCEDURES

This study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The design allow for the description of variables as they exist in their natural settings. The population of the study comprises of one hundred and thirty-two (132) Business Educators in public own tertiary institutions in Delta State (Delta State University, Abraka (17), University of Delta, Agbor (18), College of Education Mosogar (10), College of Education, Warri (10), and Federal College of Education, (Technical), Asaba (77). The entire population was used for the study hence, census sampling technique was used. A structured self-designed questionnaire was utilized for data collection. The research instrument consisted of sections A and B. Section A was made up of the demographic variables of the respondents such as gender and type of institution. While section B was made up of two parts with a total of 20 questionnaire items. Each part contained 10 items.

The items in section B were rated on a 4-point likert type rating scale from Highly Required (HR = 4), Required (R = 3), Slightly Required (SR = 2) and Not Required (NR = 1). The instrument was face and content validated by three (3) experts, two experts from the Department of Business Education and one expert from Measurement and Evaluation unit, all from Delta State University, Abraka. These experts analyze each item in the questionnaires to ascertain their adequacy in measuring what they set to measure and all errors was corrected before the final copy or draft.

The researcher with the help of five research assistants one from each institution administered the questionnaire on the respondents. The research assistants were brief on the purpose of the study, questionnaire distribution and collection. The researcher and research assistants administered the instrument on the respondents. Completed copies of the questionnaire were checked to ensure that they were properly filled. The retrieved questionnaire were used to obtain data for analysis. A total number of one hundred and thirty-two (132) questionnaires were administered and retrieved, making 100% return rate

Data collected were analyzed using SPSS Version 24. Mean (\bar{X}) and Standard Deviation (SD) were used to answer research questions while t-test was used for testing the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Any calculated Mean (\bar{X}) that is less than 2.50 means Not Required while any calculated Mean (\bar{X}) that is 2.50 and above means Required. For the hypotheses, any calculated p-value that is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected and any calculated p-value that is 0.05 and above, the null hypothesis was retained.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What are the time management skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State?*

Table .1: Mean and Standard Deviation responses of business educators on time management skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process

S/N	Statement items	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
	Time management skills required for effective recruitment and selection process			
1.	Goal-setting	3.51	0.56	Required
2.	Prioritization	3.07	0.38	Required
3.	Scheduling	3.57	0.60	Required
4.	Time allocation	3.70	0.61	Required
5.	Organization	3.46	0.52	Required
6.	Avoid procrastination	3.47	0.52	Required
7.	Focus and concentration	3.69	0.51	Required
8.	Delegation	3.30	0.48	Required
9.	Adaptability	3.14	0.43	Required
10.	Technology and tool management	3.33	0.47	Required
	Cluster Mean/SD	3.42	0.51	Required

Source: Field Work (2024)

Data presented in Table 1 indicated that the mean responses of respondents on time management skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions varied from 3.07 to 3.70, while the standard deviation ranged from 0.38 to 0.61. Similarly, the cluster mean of 3.42 portrays that time management skills are required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Also, the standard deviation illustrates that the respondents were not far apart in their responses.

Research Question 2: *What are the digital skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation responses of business educators on digital skill required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process

S/N	Statement items	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
	Digital skills required for effective recruitment and selection process			
11.	Basic computer skills	3.85	0.44	Required
12.	Internet skills	3.54	0.56	Required
13.	Word processing skills	3.82	0.50	Required
14.	Email skills	3.39	0.52	Required
15.	Spreadsheets skills	3.36	0.57	Required
16.	Presentation skills	3.37	0.52	Required
17.	Digital communication skills	3.34	0.54	Required
18.	Data analysis skills	3.26	0.61	Required
19.	Online collaboration skills	3.29	0.57	Required
20.	Emerging technology skills	3.39	0.52	Required
	Cluster Mean/SD	3.46	0.54	Required

Data presented in Table 2 revealed that the mean responses of respondents on digital skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions ranged from 3.26 to 3.85, while the standard deviation ranged from 0.44 to 0.61. Also, the cluster mean of 3.46 indicated that digital skills are required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Also, the standard deviation signified that the respondents were close in their responses.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of business educators on time management skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State based on gender.

Table 3: t-test Analysis of time management skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State based on gender.

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	α	t	p-value	Decision
Male	77	3.52	0.58	130	0.05	0.29	0.77	Not Significant
Female	55	3.49	0.54					

Data presented in Table 3 revealed that the t-value on time management skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process is 0.29 while the p-value is 0.77. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of business educators on time management skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State based on gender. Hence, the null hypothesis of no significant difference was retained.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of business educators on digital skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State based on type of institution

Table 4: t-test Analysis of digital skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State based on type of institution.

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	α	t	p-value	Decision
Colleges of Education	97	3.88	0.39	130	0.05	1.22	0.23	Not Significant
Universities	35	3.77	0.55					

Data presented in Table 4 revealed that the t-value on digital skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process is 1.22 while the p-value is 0.23. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of business educators on digital skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State based on type of institution. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference was retained.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study found that business educators require job productivity skills for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State. From the findings it was discovered that business educators are required to possess time management skills for them to be recruited and selected for employment in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The time management skills they are required to possess include goal-setting, prioritization, scheduling, time allocation, organization, avoiding procrastination, focus and concentration, delegation, adaptability and technology and tool management. The finding is in harmony with Grimm (2011) who found that a well time management skill staff increases organizational productivity. Again, in support of this finding is Lukevich and Wigmore, (2024), who upheld that organization that have employees that possess effective time management skills stand to have happier employees, improved creativity, less absenteeism, lower turnover rate, increased productivity and enhanced reputation.

The result of data analysis on research question two showed that business educators are required to possess digital skills for them to be recruited and selected for employment in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The study discovered that business educators should possess the following digital skills: Basic computer skills, internet skills, word processing skills, email skills, spreadsheets skills, presentation skills, digital communication skills, data analysis skills, online collaboration skills and emerging technology skills. This finding is in harmony with the findings of Ezoem et al. (2024) who discovered that digital marketing competencies and digital social media competencies are highly needed of business education graduates employability prospect and job creation in Delta State. Also, the finding is in agreement with Dibbari and Lawrence (2023) who found that all digital skills were

required for employability by OTM students based on the opinion of business educators. This finding contradicts the findings of Ukata and Amini (2022) who found that the digital marketing and social media skills acquired was very low level.

The result of hypothesis one revealed that there was no significant difference in the mean responses of business educators on time management skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State based on gender. This finding is in conformity with the findings of Igbongidi (2021) who found in their study that equal opportunity was given to male and female employees based on merit. Again, the outcome of the study is in support of Ezoem et al. (2024) who found that gender do not significantly influenced lecturers of business education mean ratings regarding digital marketing and digital social media competencies needed of business education graduates for employability prospect and job creation in Delta State.

The findings of hypothesis two indicated that there was no significant difference in the mean responses of business educators on digital skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State based on type of institution. This result is in conformity with the findings of Okon (2023) who found that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of respondents on digital skills needed by business education students in the colleges of education and universities in Enugu State. Also, the finding is in harmony with Akpojotor (2023) who found that there was no significant difference in the relationship between job design techniques and job satisfaction of universities and colleges of education business educators in Edo and Delta States.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that business educators requires job productivity skills such as time management skills and digital skills for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The study also concluded that there was no significant difference in the mean responses of business educators on time management and digital skills required by business educators for effective recruitment and selection process in tertiary institutions in Delta State based on gender and type of institution.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Curriculum planners should ensure the inclusion of courses that will promote job productivity skills in the curriculum of business education. With this, the business educators will be able to possess these job productivity skills required by employers for recruiting and selecting candidates for employment in organizations.
2. Management should encourage lecturers to teach students those courses that promote job productivity skills as employers of labour in the 21st century require these skills for employment of workers.
3. Human resource managers should be fair in their recruitment and selection processes given applicants' equal opportunity by way of recruiting and selecting candidates that possess these job productivity skills, as employees that have good job productivity skills will help to boost the job productivity of the organization.

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